

D1.2 Strategic Roadmap

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Date: 28.02.2025

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004984

Project Acronym: CLS INFRA

Project Full Title: Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure

Grant Agreement No.: 101004984

Deliverable/Document Information

Deliverable No.: D1.2

Deliverable Title: Strategic Roadmap

Authors: Vera Yakupova: Investigation (lead); writing - original draft (lead); visualization (lead). Jennifer Edmond: Conceptualization (lead); supervision (lead); writing - review and editing (lead). Maciej Eder: Writing - review and editing (supporting).

Dissemination Level: PUBLIC

Document History

Version/Date	Changes/Approval	Author/Approved by
V0.1 30/10/2024	First Draft	Jennifer Edmond & Vera Yakupova
V0.2 13/12/2024	Second Draft	Jennifer Edmond & Vera Yakupova
V1.0 28/02/2025	Final Draft	Jennifer Edmond, Vera Yakupova, Maciej Eder

Contents

Abstract.....	4
Introduction.....	5
The Cost of Fragmentation.....	7
Optimising for Interdisciplinarity.....	11
Technological futures.....	14
Foundational Structures.....	17
Conclusion.....	19
References.....	21

Abstract

Computational Literary Studies (CLS) is facing important developments, with newly emerging technologies and evolving research infrastructures rapidly shaping its future. While the field has already made important contributions in applying computational methods to literary research, challenges such as fragmented tools, lack of sustainable data pathways, and limited interdisciplinary integration endure. This roadmap identifies key areas for future development, such as shared technical infrastructures, reproducible and exemplary workflows, and closer collaboration between computational and traditional literary studies scholars. The integration of Linked Open Data (LOD) and Large Language Models (LLMs) offers new opportunities for more advanced, interconnected and better annotated CLS research, however, their implementation requires careful consideration as pertains to accessibility, transparency, and long-term sustainability. Additionally, fostering a global community of practice and embedding CLS methodologies into broader literary scholarship will be crucial for securing its place in the future of the humanities. By addressing these challenges, CLS can move toward a more cohesive and sustainable research ecosystem.

Introduction

Computational Literary Studies (CLS) is a rapidly evolving field that applies computational methods to literary research. By applying computational tools such as text mining, natural language processing, and machine learning, CLS has opened up new pathways for exploring literary patterns, genres, and historical trends. The field, however, still faces obstacles for long-term sustainability. The fragmentation of data infrastructures, tools and workflows complicates collaboration and reproducibility, limiting the findability and reusability of research outputs. Moreover, the gap between traditional literary studies and computational approaches obstructs CLS from better integrating into broader literary scholarship, leaving questions about its future direction.

This strategic roadmap emerged from the work of the Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure (CLS INFRA) project. It identifies key areas for improvement, including the need to build sustainable pathways for tools and data, develop shared technical infrastructures, and optimise for interdisciplinary collaboration. Additionally, it emphasises the importance of integrating reproducible research practices into digital projects to ensure long-term impact. The roadmap also highlights the potential of emerging technologies, such as Linked Open Data (LOD) and Large Language Models (LLMs), to advance research practices and address some of the field's ongoing challenges. Through better integration of collaborative working environments, the reproducibility of research, and by addressing the professional needs of scholars, CLS can move toward a more cohesive and sustainable future. The areas discussed in this roadmap serve as a vision for how the field can develop into a more integrated and resilient research ecosystem, bridging the gap between computational and traditional literary methods.

The roadmap is divided into four main sections. 1) “The Cost of Fragmentation” discusses the issue of fragmentation such as the discontinuity between research projects, a lack of sustainable pathways for tools and data, the challenge of reproducing CLS results, and the need for a shared infrastructure that is more than a list of tools holding it together. 2) The section “Optimising for Interdisciplinarity” argues that there is still a gap in between NLP and literary studies in the CLS field. Among others, this is caused by the lack of

community-wide workflows and insufficient annotation. To fill these gaps, building research scenarios needs to be built into the infrastructural funding. 3) The section on “Technological Futures” discusses the opportunities for the CLS field granted through Large Language Models (LLMs) and Linked Open Data (LOD), as well as technological futures within the extraction of metadata and its conversion to RDF, living corpora, dockerisation, collaborative work environments, and validation instruments in CLS. 4) Lastly, the section focusing on “Foundational structures”, suggests efforts and issues for building a global community of practice. Such a community can be strengthened by sharing professional requirements on all projects more effectively, by thinking about advocacy and speakers for the CLS field, and by reaching target audiences for CLS outputs.

The Cost of Fragmentation

CLS is developing in an environment that is inherently fragmented, where researchers use diverse tools and methods that are not always compatible. This reality reflects the field's innovative nature, but it also brings a cost, limiting collaboration, expansion, and the long-term sustainability of research outputs. This fragmentation can be seen from a number of perspectives: 1) a fragmented data landscape of corpora and tools, 2) the fragmentation of services and hosting platforms, 3) a fragmentation of approaches and knowledge. The lack of centralised infrastructure this reflects can also often result in duplicated efforts and inconsistent data management practices. This atomised environment creates barriers to reusing tools and datasets across projects and threatens project-based work, resulting in “orphaned sources”, that are neither sustainable nor findable, even in the short term. In the longer term, the situation can become much worse, with project outputs disappearing along with the services and platforms hosting them.

As Smithies et al. put it:

A generation of legacy projects that need maintenance but are out of funding have reached critical stages of their lifecycles, an increasingly hostile security context has made DH projects potential attack vectors into institutional networks, heterogeneous and often delicate technologies have complicated the task of maintenance, and an increasing number of emerging formats have made archiving and preservation yet more difficult. (2019, 604-605)

Such instability threatens not only the progress of the field, but, ultimately, the validity of research findings, as knowledge provenance cannot be tested or traced.

Thus, many legacy digital humanities projects are at risk of becoming lost and/or fragmented due to outdated systems, insufficient maintenance, and lack of continued funding. This situation is worsened by the growing complexity of digital infrastructures and the “increasingly hostile security context” Smithies et. al. describe above. Once the funding for a project runs out, in some cases, researchers will rely on their home institution's or indeed personal funds to maintain the hosting of the project outputs, a clearly unsystematic and unsustainable, but all too common, practice. Even in the best case scenario, when another similar project in the field or an adjacent field is able to take over the hosting of some earlier

outputs, there is almost inevitably a lack of continuity between the projects, again threatening the breaking of chains of knowledge validity and transfer. At a broader, meta-level, this discontinuity can result in the loss of the discipline's history, making it difficult to build upon past advancements. Smithies et al. also observed that the survival of many projects' digital resources relies on the "goodwill of colleagues and the host institution" to maintain them, as "funders *themselves* signalled that they did not expect (or were not prepared to support) the development of long-term or permanent digital resources" (2019, 607).

A related issue to this is **the lack of clear sustainable pathways for tools and data**. This includes how to maintain and valorise non-textual scholarly objects. CLS is an interdisciplinary field and produces many scholarly objects that go far beyond textual articles. Although there are some good practice exemplars, in particular in the sciences, scholarly platforms and academic journals will need to expand their support for publications made up of a wider range of diverse objects that comprise the scholarly argument, not only the text data or data dumps, but potentially also software analysis tools and in some cases dynamic interfaces. CLS INFRA has addressed these challenges through some of its experimental work, reflected in its Deliverables D3.2 and D5.3. These two deliverables, and particularly D3.2, test out new ways of publishing CLS results through an interactive textbook that can be read either vertically, horizontally, or just linearly. There is, of course, much more work of this type to be done.

Furthermore, there is still a **fragmented landscape of corpora**, the development of which has been driven by individual interests, copyright windows, and what happens to be accessed or accessible, lacking any sort of strategic approach. CLS researchers often do more research on corpora that are accessible, as opposed to corpora of their research interest. Despite the availability of numerous digital libraries, a lack of standardisation complicates access and reuse of resources (Börner et al. 2024). But access alone will not fully enliven the field. There also will need to be better data integration and the development of data models to facilitate better access and usability of these resources (Börner et al. 2024). For the field of CLS to truly flourish, future corpora would need to not only cover those gaps but also be accessible for use.

The cost of fragmentation in the field of CLS thus also affects **issues of reproducibility**. Different parameters, pipelines, and the packaging of visualisations, data, and results make it challenging to replicate findings. CLS research projects struggle to provide user-friendly interfaces and ensure the reproducibility of their resources. For better reproducibility, researchers need to have access to the data and workflows of the researchers whose findings they are assessing, ideally encompassing the full technological stack used in a project. Achieving reproducibility in CLS demands additional labour, even when infrastructures are in place. This effort includes the documentation of data sources, pre-processing steps, analytical methods, and interpretative frameworks to enable other researchers to replicate studies. Moreover, the interdisciplinary nature of CLS often requires collaboration among scholars from diverse fields, each with distinct methodologies and terminologies. Coordinating these efforts necessitates clear communication and comprehensive documentation to maintain consistency and reproducibility across the research team. Despite existing infrastructures, the complexity of literary data and the nuanced interpretations involved add layers of difficulty to achieving reproducible results. Therefore, dedicated labour in the form of thorough documentation, standardized workflows, and continuous collaboration is essential to uphold the standards of reproducible research in CLS. The future of CLS needs more research to consolidate CLS practices, capture sustainable CLS workflows, and validate CLS methods. “[M]ost research that repeated earlier research also aims to be repeatable, because this kind of repeatability, closely related to transparency and sustainability, is something that researchers come to value when they practice the hardships of repeating earlier research” (Schöch 2023, 374). Reproducible research plays an important role in building knowledge by reinforcing core values such as reliability and trustworthiness. It represents an ongoing cycle, “a (never identical) reenactment of past research, and an invitation for (never identical) further reenactments in the future,” contributing to a productive, iterative research process (Schöch 2023, 374). Schöch suggests a framework distinguishing between replication, reproduction, and reanalysis, aimed at fostering transparency and sustainability in computational studies. He emphasises the importance of reproducibility and reuse, arguing that these practices enhance the reliability and scholarly value of digital humanities research. Ensuring the reproducibility of research can therefore function as a foundational practice for validating and advancing computational methods within the humanities (Schöch 2023).

Moreover, while there are some elements of a **shared technical infrastructure**, the CLS community needs more than a list of tools to be bound together cohesively. In the CLS INFRA project, the transformation toolbox (Ďurčo et al. 2023) and the DraCor Programmable Corpora (Fischer 2019) serve as examples of light integration, utilising tools located elsewhere to create functional connections, for example by exposing data via APIs. However, this integration is largely structural; there is no semantic interoperability, meaning services cannot effectively communicate with each other. To address this, we would need further exemplary workflows and methods to connect diverse toolchains for these tools to ensure interoperability and a smoother collaborative process.

Optimising for Interdisciplinarity

The fragmentation of the infrastructural environment for CLS must be understood in the context of fragmentation of the field as a whole. In spite of decades of predictions of the ‘post-digital’ humanities, **a gap remains between CLS and traditional literary studies**. In fact, there are indications of the literary and the computational approach diverging rather than converging. The divide between literary and computational methods impedes conversations on the development of computational literary studies research, “[y]et the perception of a divide remains, and it prevents effective critiques of reductive uses of computation (in literary studies and beyond) or productive engagements with computation’s constitutive effects (including for literary textuality and subjectivity)” (Bode 2023, 507). Kopec argues that there is a value difference between literary and digital humanities scholars. Some literary scholars advocate for new formalism which defends tradition (close reading), while digital humanists can sometimes seem to speak more for postindustrial values like teamwork and adaptability to address broader challenges (2016, 326-328). They also argue that these two movements are distinct responses to “corporatization” and defunding (Kopec 2016, 325) in literary studies. In a previous article Bode (2022) argued for a balanced literary and computational approach to computational literary studies, questioning the "data-centric" perspective that often defines this field. She questions the assumption that computational tools alone can provide comprehensive insights into literature, emphasising the need to integrate computational methods with traditional interpretative techniques. Bode calls for an interdisciplinary approach that respects the complexity of literary studies, suggesting that purely computational methods should not overshadow the contextual and interpretative depth essential to literary analysis. There are tools available to assist with this: annotation models, for example, provide the opportunity to connect text with numbers, but there remains the barrier that the literary text as a whole is not visible anymore in human readable form.

To further navigate the interdisciplinarity of CLS and bring together researchers with NLP and literary studies backgrounds, one mechanism would be to ensure **the incorporation of research scenarios into infrastructural funding**. Every infrastructure that produces tools should be able to demonstrate use cases and present relevant research scenarios and pointers for the wider adoption of the workflows that underpin them. That said, it is often difficult to

predict how people from various fields will use CLS tools, and a person responsible for developing CLS tools may not be in a particularly good position to know if their tools are valid according to a literary research paradigm and values. Infrastructures therefore require ‘translators’ or ‘mediators’, given the relative rarity of truly ‘bilingual’ CLS researchers. Until these kinds of bridging people and artifacts can be built, literary scholars will continue to shy away from CLS research, believing they do not have the required technical knowledge to validate the method’s results. Similarly, researchers with a computer science or computational linguistics background might either hesitate to engage with literary texts, adapt tools for CLS, or (perhaps worse yet) might promote methods that are fully at odds with the traditional of literary hermeneutics. Due to the interdisciplinary nature of the CLS field, there is a growing need for scholars who can operate across these disciplinary boundaries, acting as "mediators" between technical and research-specific needs. Without such boundary-crossers, there will always be a risk of creating disciplinary silos—where tools and data are confined to small, isolated communities—particularly as annotation and model training practices vary widely across fields (Schöch et al., 2023). This need not require huge investment, but a change in values and priorities: for example, workflows and documentation could enable a person not trained in NLP to use the tools and understand the valid data and evidence collection, though it should be recognised that what they want from it and the depth to which they wish to go with the tools may be different. Widening such practices will help overcome the phenomenon of malfunctioning ‘boundary objects’ that seem to build communication between disciplinary communities, but in fact may do the opposite. For instance, literary and computational scholars often interpret terms such as ‘data’ or ‘evidence’ differently, and might also approach working with and interpreting models based on literary works differently. Truly interdisciplinary contexts need new kinds of scholars who dare to step beyond their discipline of expertise and who seek to collaborate with other disciplines.

Similarly, the current lack of **community-wide workflows** further complicates entry into the field for people looking to use its many and varied tools. Rather than viewing the plurality of tools as a problem to be fixed, however, it may be more productive to find ways to work within this diverse ecosystem, encouraging greater collaboration across disciplines. The separation of roles, eg. between infrastructure developers and users, often results in a gap between infrastructure capabilities and their practical applications (Schöch, Dudar, and Fileva

2023). Outlining workflows and toolchains can bridge this gap and will contribute to the relevance and use of these tools. These initiatives will need funding in and of themselves, however: unless forms of documentation that support reuse and adaptation can be rewarded as both resource-hungry, collaboratively intense, and deeply scholarly, we cannot expect these kinds of instruments to become commonplace. For the creation of workflows, the “users of digital tools should be thoroughly involved in their design” or the project will end up with “sophisticated computational tools that were of great interest to computer scientists, but were often met with indifference by the scholars who were supposed to use them” (Kaltenbrunner 2015, 227).

Annotation is a further example of a mechanism that can help, as it represents the knowledge of the field being build into the system. This often tedious work can be essential to align corpora, however, and ensure the rich context needed for humanities interpretation is available. CLS will need fit-for-purpose support infrastructure for more standardised annotation schemes, especially to facilitate research across languages.

Creating guidelines [for annotation] that are widely applicable, however, is almost only possible in large annotation projects, which are naturally expensive. Moreover, scholars interested in large-scale analyses of literary texts are required to perform a lot of tasks that are outside of their core expertise, while researchers from computer science interested in method development for literary texts are required to create annotated data by themselves. (Reiter, Willand and Gius 2019, 1)

Consistent annotation in CLS scholarship could be a way of integrating the underlying (literary) textual data more transparently. As Bories, Fabo and Plecháč say, through annotation, we “address textual objects at both a holistic and an analytical level, blend systematic and intuitive reasoning routines, navigate linear and iterative processes, and, of course, integrate distant and close reading” (2022, 226).

Technological futures

As a field with a significant technological dependency, and future-looking consideration of the development of CLS must take this aspect into account. Hatzel et al. (2023) reviewed existing literature in CLS and discussed how machine learning models, have been applied for tasks like sentiment analysis, stylometry, and text classification. Traditional machine learning methods, such as those that support vector-based approaches and logistic regression, allow for transparency and alignment with interpretative analysis in CLS. However, transformer-based models are increasingly used to detect intricate language patterns and semantic structures, despite the challenges of using them with historical and complex literary texts. Although there are many developments that could in theory direct the course of the field, the two most likely to have near-term significant impact are Linked Open Data (LOD) and Large Language Models (LLMs). These are both developing quickly, with LOD improving data sharing and interoperability, and LLMs offering new possibilities for textual analysis. Both technologies, however, require careful integration to avoid bias and improve transparency.

Advancing emerging technologies, particularly **LOD and LLMs, should therefore be progressed as a matter of urgency** with the goal of expanding the horizons of CLS, but also enhancing its reproducibility and lowering barriers to entry. While many recent projects focus on disambiguating existing resources, they often fail to produce new structured data or triples which would be able to expand shared knowledge spaces. Without comprehensive metadata, corpora are incomplete and less useful for scholarly research. LOD allows for bibliographies, texts, and other resources to be integrated into interconnected knowledge graphs. These shared spaces allow for more dynamic interactions with data, such as transforming prompts into SPARQL queries and using LLMs to generate answers based on returned results. Such developments offer new interface opportunities and could change how researchers engage with literary data.

Large language models (LLMs) could also help with the annotation process in CLS: “the few-shot capabilities of LLMs could help scale annotations more quickly and simpler than traditional training approaches. That is to say, given only very few manually annotated examples, a large body of text could be automatically annotated with the given annotation

schema for a specific concept allowing for corpus level analysis” (Hatzel et al. 2023, 211). LLMs could be used for part-of-speech tagging in literary works: “fine-tuning Large Language Models like OpenAI’s GPT-3.5-Turbo can significantly heighten accuracy in part-of-speech tagging performance” (Stüssi and Ströbel 2024, 204). In addition, machine learning models are being used to facilitate tasks such as character analysis, shedding light on the “people in the narrated world” (Hatzel et al., 2023, 211), narrative modeling, “i.e. modeling what happens on the story level by building up from computationally analyzing surface phenomena” (Hatzel et al., 2023, 212), and thematic clustering and topic modelling (Hatzel et al., 2023, 203). Nevertheless the two main challenges that CLS faces are: “the black-box nature of some machine learning models and ... tying results generated by machine learning methods back to literary theory ... to gain insights” (Hatzel et al. 2023, 213). Traditional ML approaches, such as SVMs and feature-based models, are also still relevant due to their interpretability, using techniques like n-grams and TF-IDF (Hatzel et al. 2023, 205). The future of CLS lies in integrating large language models with literary methodologies, fostering interdisciplinary collaborations to align computational methods with humanistic theories. This advancement promises to streamline data processing, enhance interpretability, and expand the scope of CLS by bridging the gap between computational efficiency and nuanced literary analysis. This synergy of computational labour with humanistic interpretation will have AI support rather than replace traditional literary scholarship, thus not disconnecting the research results from the literary text.

Furthermore, **the process of extracting metadata and converting it to RDF**, initiated during the CLS INFRA project, can be continued opportunistically to make corpora more findable. Making corpora more findable requires a multi-step approach: first, corpora should be registered to ensure their presence in searchable catalogues. Second, basic metadata can be extracted and converted into RDF format, creating structured, machine-readable data that facilitates better integration into shared knowledge spaces. Finally, there is an opportunity to further enrich the metadata, allowing for more advanced and nuanced search capabilities. Most importantly, this process focuses on improving accessibility and usability without altering the original data, so that the integrity of the primary resources remains intact. Projects focusing on RDF metadata extraction have demonstrated how registering corpora and linking them to basic metadata can serve as a foundation for more sophisticated enhancements. Transitioning to RDF can make “data more easily shareable and setting up

data to have meaning and relationships as opposed to local static description that requires programmatic interpretation” (Hardesty 2016, 59). The reality of that shows that transitioning “an XML standard to RDF does not make that data more shareable or more easily understood unless there are end user applications for using that data in RDF” (Hardesty 2016, 59). Hardesty also notes that it “is vital to understand that transitioning from XML to RDF requires a shift in perspective from replicating structures in XML to defining meaningful relationships in RDF” (2016, 60). Thus, where the relationships in the RDF are clearly defined, they can significantly contribute to the sustainability of corpora by making them more discoverable.

Another influential approach is that of the **living corpora**, found in the dynamic collections of texts or data that evolve over time, continuously incorporating new materials. Unlike traditional corpora, which are fixed and unchanging, living corpora undergo regular updates, with each version capturing the state of the corpus at a specific point in time. This flexibility allows researchers to work with the most current and comprehensive datasets, integrating new texts, annotations, and metadata as they become available. Living corpora are often maintained through collaborative efforts across institutions and research groups, making them open to ongoing contributions and improvements. They also help with research on evolving language use and cultural trends. However, one of the key challenges with living corpora is the lack of clear versioning in reproducibility studies. Researchers rarely cite commits, which are essential for tracking specific versions of a corpus at a given point in time. Without this, it becomes difficult to verify the exact dataset used in a study. Alongside this issue, many APIs providing access to these corpora don’t offer commit information either, further complicating reproducibility. To address this, there should be a greater emphasis on citing commits and version tracking in APIs as part of their functionality.

Many researchers believe that **Docker** may provide an avenue to create more coherence and promote sustainability in the variable landscape of technology. CLS researchers would need to further define what the limits of Docker usage might be and what skills would be needed to promote reuse of these formats. Tools packaged within Docker containers become more accessible and easier to maintain across varying computational platforms. However, its adoption may be challenging for users who do not feel skilled enough to effectively access

and manage Docker environments. These skill gaps would need to be addressed if Dockerisation is to serve as a scalable solution for research reproducibility and a wider user base for the tools.

The technological future of CLS might also be enhanced by the further development of **collaborative working environments and shared validation instruments**. Especially within a research community that is increasingly international and interdisciplinary, the future of collaboration across diverse research communities will increasingly rely on such platforms, which are able to record and ensure provenance and promote communications. One such example is Madoc (Universiteit Gent 2024), an open-source platform designed for managing, enriching, and curating IIF-based digital collections. Developed by Digirati, it integrates multiple open-source technologies and web standards, such as IIF (International Image Interoperability Framework), W3C Web Annotations, and Linked Data, to provide a unified interface for working with digital objects. Madoc allows researchers and institutions to assemble digital collections from diverse archives, libraries, and museums, and build interactive websites around them. Users can import metadata and annotations, such as OCR text or image segmentations, and enhance them with editorial content. The platform also supports participatory annotation, allowing for users to add transcriptions, translations, tags, and commentaries to digital objects. Bringing together these kinds of functionalities into easy-to-use environments could provide not only more fluid communications, but greater visibility and reusability of the resources they contain, holding the communities that work through them together in a more effective way.

Foundational Structures

Research infrastructure must align with the fundamental research requirements of the field it serves, but ultimately it can only provide stability through **professional and stable management**. Unlike research tools and workflows, this is not something that varies greatly between fields and communities, and yet it is a key potential success factor (or failure point) for CLS infrastructure. Organisation will not organise itself. For this reason, professional requirements on multiple projects serving the broad CLS community should be documented or indeed shared more effectively. Communications tasks, for example, represent a skillset in

themselves, but one which can have a huge impact on the success of researcher uptake. As such, the knowledge and experience to deliver these tasks could become a shared asset, or indeed an element in future projects that is reviewed and valorised to ensure that research partners collaborate seamlessly.

There is a further, wider challenge inherent in the communications and organisation tasks described above. Given the diversity and fragmentation of the CLS field, it can be difficult to determine who represents it, who can advocate for it, or speak for its needs. **Advocacy** plays a crucial role in this context and individuals need to be trained within the field to clearly articulate its value and its diverse applications, a shared understanding of CLS and the field's developments can foster its further potential. Researchers and practitioners advocating and speaking for the field will have to develop value propositions that allow them to build bridges across disciplines and reach broader audiences. Furthermore, although no one voice could ever encompass the full complexity of CLS, having centralised, shared set of messages and indeed recognisable organisational leadership would be a significant asset.

One particular challenge in this respect would be the need to build a global presence for the field. Building and maintaining a **global community of practice** is not simple: it would require venues for shared conversations about methodologies reaching across not just languages but highly varied national and regional infrastructural and resource landscapes. The benefits of such connection would, however, address a fragmented ecosystem and can help to gain the benefits of scale, such as broader knowledge sharing and resource accessibility, even within a decentralised structure. However, cohesion within such a diverse and dispersed community would require intentional strategies. According to Wenger, McDermott, and Snyder (2002), building a global community of practice relies on mechanisms that encourage continuous dialogue, shared learning, and the establishment of common goals. Cataldo (2009) summarises the following steps for building a community of practice: “(1) design for evolution, (2) open a dialogue between inside and outside perspectives, (3) invite different levels of participation, (4) develop both public and private community spaces, (5) focus on value, (6) combine familiarity and excitement, and (7) create a rhythm for the communities” (302).

Lastly, the outputs and methods from CLS have value beyond literary research. **Reaching these broader audiences**, in particular those beyond the circle of academic research, will require targeted dissemination strategies and the development of good practice exemplars and accessible tools. Engaging with non-specialist audiences through welcoming formats—such as workshops, open-access publications, or transdisciplinary collaboration—could also improve the visibility and impact of CLS research. To advance the field, CLS researchers should actively pursue opportunities for applied and transdisciplinary engagement and communication.

Conclusion

This strategic roadmap for Computational Literary Studies (CLS) thus outlines a path toward addressing the field's most pressing challenges, particularly the fragmentation of tools, data, and workflows that stand in the way to long-term sustainability. By building shared infrastructures, promoting reproducibility, and encouraging interdisciplinary collaboration, CLS can evolve into a more cohesive and accessible research ecosystem. This roadmap also emphasizes the importance of integrating emerging technologies, such as Linked Open Data (LOD) and Large Language Models (LLMs), which can change how literary research is conducted and shared. However, realising these goals will require more than technological advancement, and will depend on creating collaborative working environments and establishing community-wide workflows that support both traditional and computational scholars. The future of CLS lies in balancing innovation with sustainability, ensuring that the field remains adaptable and relevant while maintaining the humanistic values that have defined the traditional literary studies. With these steps in place, CLS can bridge the gap between traditional literary scholarship and digital methodologies, ultimately shaping the way we engage with literature in the digital age.

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